

International Conference

"Sustainable Development in a Multipolar Society"

Hybrid – online & in-person

November 15, 2024, Harvard, UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

Registration of the participants	09.00-09.30
Event welcome	09.30-09.45
Plenary speakers	09.45-13.00
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i> Strategizing Development in a Multipolar Society: Harmonizing Growth, Geopolitical Interests, and Social Equity in an Era of Global Power Shifts	09.45-10.45
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society: Balancing Environmental Stewardship, Economic Equity, and Diversity in a Fragmented Global Landscape	10.45-11.45
Q & A	11.45-13.00
Parallel sessions	13.00-16.30
<i>Session 1 – Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society: Addressing Global Challenges, Regional Disparities, and Collaborative Approaches for a Resilient Future	13.00-13.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i> Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society: Bridging Geopolitical Differences, Economic Inequalities, and Collaborative	13.30-14.00

Strategies for Global Environmental Stewardship	
<p><i>Session 2 – Global Development in a Multipolar World</i></p> <p><i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i></p> <p><i>Austria</i></p> <p>Global Development in a Multipolar World: Navigating Geopolitical Shifts, Economic Diversification, and Collaborative Growth Strategies</p>	13.00-13.30
<p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandia Agency UK</i></p> <p>Global Development in a Multipolar World: Addressing Geopolitical Dynamics, Economic Transformation, and the Role of Multilateral Cooperation in Shaping Future Growth</p>	13.30-14.00
Coffee break	14.00-14.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p>Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society: Harmonizing Diverse Global Perspectives, Policy Approaches, and Collaborative Actions for Sustainable Development</p>	14.15-14.45
<p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p>Navigating Sustainability in a Multipolar Society: Exploring Cross-Cultural Perspectives, Geopolitical Dynamics, and Collaborative Frameworks for Global Environmental Solutions</p>	14.45-15.15
<p><i>Session 2 – Global Development in a Multipolar World</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p>Global Development in a Multipolar World: Analyzing Geopolitical Realignments, Economic Reshaping, and the Future of International Cooperation</p>	14.15-14.45
<p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p>Global Development in a Multipolar World: Exploring the Implications of Emerging Powers, Economic Shifts, and New Models of Global Governance</p>	14.45-15.15

CBM International University USA

Akados Learning UK

9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

Q&A	15.15-16.00
Concluding remarks	16.00-16.30

Location: Cambridge - Harvard Square-Mifflin Place, Harvard Square, Cambridge,
02138, United States of America